

E-VOLVE EV FOR LIFE, VALUE, EFFICIENCY

NEWSLETTER 10/24

Summer is over, the leaves have turned colours and the cluster projects could not be busier! We have a brand-new newsletter for you with lots of news about our co-operation with 2ZERO, some great papers and prototypes that have been released in the projects and many fun events we have attended. Additionally, we are organizing a new E-VOLVE Cluster webinar this November and invite you to save the date. We hope you enjoy this issue of our newsletter as much as we do, because we could not be more excited for the next few months!

E-VOLVE Cluster & 2ZERO

Research Need	HiPE	HighSCAPE	RHODaS	SCAPE	EM-TECH	Powerdrive	MAXIMA	V-LTCRR	SmartCorners	EFFEREST	HEFT	MINDED
Vehicle technologies and vehicle propulsion solutions for BEV and FCEV												
conceptual vehicle design	sec	sec		sec					core	core		
zero emission HDV	sec			sec								
energy efficient and user-centric interiors		sec				sec			core	core		core
advanced lightweight design for zero emissions							sec					core
digitalization enabled advanced design methods		sec	core		sec	sec	core	core	sec	sec	sec	sec
efficient control of vehicle operations	sec	core	sec		core		sec	sec	core	core	core	core
powertrain modularity and integration	core	core	core	core	core	core	core	core	core	sec	core	
integration of battery systems				sec								
thermal management	core	core	sec	sec	sec	core	core	core	core	core	sec	core
charging systems: fast, wireless				sec		core						
Tyres and brakes		sec							sec			
safety			sec									
Integration of BEV in energy system and charging infrastructure												
charging infrastructure												
interoperability of charging infrastructure												
system approach of battery based e-mobility												
planning BEV connectivity for system approach												
fast high power charging												
Zero tailpipe emission mobility for people and goods												
pathways towards zero emissions									sec			
connected and shared e-services												
user-need driven right-sized vehicles and infrastructure requirements								sec	sec	sec		sec
mobility for people in urban, peri urban and rural areas						core				sec		sec
logistics concepts and solutions deployment acceleration												
LCA and Circular economy							sec					
Life cycle inventory database				core	sec							
track and trace of products and their use over life-time			core				core					
method and tools for LCA/LCC			core	sec	core			core			core	
social LCA for the transport sector					sec		core					
methods, tools and processes for CE			sec		sec			core	sec		sec	
capacity building for circular economy			sec									
system-wide LC and CE strategy modeling					core							
assessment of mobility scenarios												
CE strategies for ZEVs							sec					
LCA and CE-based mobility concepts												

Figure 1: 2ZERO mapping

The European Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) [2ZERO](#) and the European technology platform [ERTRAC](#) have developed comprehensive roadmaps and multi-annual strategic research agendas (SRIAs) aimed at driving innovation and sustainability in the transportation sector.

These initiatives focus on the decarbonisation of road transport and the advancement of electromobility, aligned with European Green Deal objectives. By identifying key priorities in sustainable mobility, they provide strategic

direction for research and development across Europe.

Within the E-VOLVE Cluster, which supports the evolution of electrified vehicles, we have undertaken a critical task: creating a mapping between active projects in the E-VOLVE Cluster and the roadmap topics outlined by 2ZERO and ERTRAC. This mapping exercise ensures that ongoing research initiatives are aligned with the broader strategic goals set out by these

E-VOLVE EV FOR LIFE, VALUE, EFFICIENCY

organizations, maximizing the impact and coherence of efforts across the ecosystem.

The mapping process not only highlights synergies between existing projects and strategic research priorities but also helps identify gaps where further development or investment may be needed. By aligning E-VOLVE Cluster projects with the roadmaps, we can enhance collaboration, avoid duplication of efforts, and focus on innovation areas that offer the most potential for the future of electric vehicle technology.

Through this integrated approach, the E-VOLVE Cluster contributes to the overarching goals of

2ZERO and ERTRAC, facilitating progress towards a zero-emission road transport system. This collaborative work is essential in meeting the European Union's climate targets and transforming the mobility landscape in a sustainable and efficient manner. The alignment of cluster activities with strategic roadmaps fosters a coordinated effort that accelerates the transition to cleaner, smarter transport solutions.

[Bernhard Brandstätter](#), Virtual Vehicle – [HIPE](#)

PROJECT NEWS

Active Gate Drivers for High-Power, High-Frequency WBG Devices

The [RHODaS](#) project has published a new public report entitled “Active Gate Drivers for High-Power, High-Frequency WBG Devices”. The report focuses on the development and evaluation of advanced gate drivers (AGDs) for high-power, high-frequency wide bandgap (WBG) devices, specifically silicon carbide (SiC) and gallium nitride (GaN) transistors. The research aims to address the challenges posed by the high-speed switching characteristics of these devices, which can lead to issues such as oscillations, overshoots, and electromagnetic interference (EMI).

One of the key innovations presented in the report is a novel gate-driving approach based on high-frequency pulse-width modulation (PWM). This method involves shaping a custom gate voltage profile to control the energy applied during the turn-on and turn-off transitions of GaN transistors.

The approach aims to reduce overshoots, oscillations, and EMI without significantly

increasing switching losses. The high-frequency PWM is generated using a field-programmable gate array (FPGA), which allows for dynamic adjustment of the gate voltage.

The research includes both simulation and experimental validation of the proposed gate-driving method. Simulations were conducted using LTspice, and the results showed a significant reduction in overshoots and oscillations compared to conventional gate drivers.

Experimental evaluations were carried out using a laboratory setup that included GaN devices, a totem-pole driver, and an FPGA. The experimental results corroborated the simulation findings, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed gate-driving technique in real-world conditions.

To read and [download the full report](#) from the RHODaS website.

[Mike Hepworth](#), KNEIA – [RHODaS](#)

Follow the project:

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EM-TECH new paper released

EM-TECH

“On-board electric powertrain control for the compensation of the longitudinal acceleration oscillations caused by road irregularities” is the topic of the latest released paper from the EM-TECH project. Our project participants Pietro Stano, Davide Lazzarini et al. are to be congratulated for their journal paper “On-board electric powertrain control for the compensation of the longitudinal acceleration oscillations caused by road irregularities”, published in Mechanism and Machine Theory, Volume 202, 2024.

Figure 2: Experimental validation of the simulation plant along the realistic road profile: PSDs of vertical and longitudinal accelerations of the sprung mass at the front axle

The [EM-TECH](#) research demonstrated that on-board electric powertrains can be used to enhance ride comfort and the longitudinal vehicle dynamics through the preview-based control of the motor torque, accounting for the road irregularities ahead through the input from road scanning sensors.

If you are interested to find out more about this paper, [follow the link](#) and get all the information.

[Davide Lazzarini](#) et al., University of Surrey/Politecnico di Torino – [EM-TECH](#)

Follow the project:

Meet the SCAPE prototypes

Halfway through its 4-year journey, the SCAPE project has reached a critical milestone in its mission to revolutionize the design and architecture of EV power converters. Recently, SCAPE unveiled two prototype models, which serve as foundational elements for the development of its final prototype. This final version will be integrated into a medium-sized electric vehicle, demonstrating both fault tolerance and efficiency in a real-world setting.

Figure 3: SCAPE's low voltage switching cell prototype

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Figure 4: SCAPE's chip-embedded high voltage switching cell thermal system

You can find extended information about [SCAPE's Switching Cell Prototype](#) by following the link or you can read more about [High-Voltage Switching Cell Prototypes with Chip Embedding Technology](#) by clicking here.

[Valentina Malcotti](#), ISINNOVA – [SCAPE](#)

Follow the SCAPE project:

CONFERENCES & EVENTS

ICEM 2024

Electric motor projects funded under the Horizon Europe call topic HORIZON-CL5-2022-D5-01-09-Nextgen EV components: High efficiency and low cost electric motors for circularity and low use of rare resources ([2ZERO](#)), including [CiiMAFlux](#), [VOLT CAR](#), [MAXIMA](#), [EM-TECH](#), and [HEFT](#), were presented at the ICEM 2024 industry session. All the projects aim at addressing the key societal challenges identified by the European Commission, as highlighted also in the Strategic Research of Innovation Agenda, SRIA, of public private partnership 2ZERO. We specifically focused on motor topologies and system designs that achieve reduced size with expected energy efficiency and costs. We also emphasized the importance of proper cooling and design choices that minimize the use of rare earth permanent magnets and enhance their recyclability. Digital tools and prototyping surely play a central role in all projects for reaching the expected outcomes. To maximize impact, [VOLT CAR](#), [MAXIMA](#), [EM-](#)

[TECH](#) and [HEFT](#) have joined the E-VOLVE cluster to enhance outreach for all projects.

Project impacts: 2Zero mapping

Research Need	☒	☒	☒	☒	☒
Vehicle technologies and vehicle propulsion solutions for BEV and PHEV					
advanced lightweight design for zero emissions			sec		core
digitalisation enabled advanced design methods	sec	core	core	sec	sec
efficient control of vehicle operations	core	sec	sec	core	sec
powertrain modularity and integration	core	core	core	core	core
thermal management		core	core	sec	sec
LCA and Circular economy					
Life cycle inventory database			sec	sec	
Track and trace of products and their use over life-time	sec		core		
method and tools for LCA/CEC		core		core	core
social LCA for the transport sector			core	sec	sec
methods, tools and processes for CE		core		sec	sec
system-wide LC and CE strategy modelling				core	
CE strategies for 2Zero			sec		

Figure 5: E-motor projects' impact mapping.

[Jenni Pippuri Mäkeläinen](#), VTT – [VOLT CAR](#)

EUROPEAN RESEARCHER'S NIGHT

The university of Graz invited interested researchers of all ages to the "European Researchers Night" under the motto "Life is Science in a World turned Upside Down". The [EM-TECH](#) project happily took the opportunity and presented many experiments with magnetism and electromagnets. From toy trains to ferrofluid, rare earth magnets and a real working e-motor

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model, kids were able to see what magnets can do, how they differ in strength and what effect electricity has on them. Children could even build their own tiny electromotor with a C-battery and copper wire.

Figure 6: EM-TECH stand (Alejandro from UrbanGold and Anna from Armengaud Innovate)

But it was not only the children who had a blast experimenting, also grown-ups calculating how many lemons it would take to replace the C-battery to build the e-motor. The European Researchers Night really is something for all ages!

Figure 7: Combining lemon batteries and mini electric motors

Across the hall, [EFFEREST](#), [HiPE](#), [greenSPEED](#) and [OpMoSi](#) also had a table where visitors of all ages could explore the fascinating world of electricity – using lemons as a power source!

Children had the chance to create their own “lemon batteries” while learning about the basics of electricity and how we rely on batteries in our everyday lives. They also looked at the advantages and disadvantages of using batteries and discussed how we can make them more efficient. And it was not just the children who were captivated by the booths – adults joined in with great enthusiasm, proving that science has no age limits. Curiosity and a love of learning make science accessible to everyone!

Figure 8: The team at the EM-TECH Stand (f.l.t.r: Florian, Marcela, Ingrid, Alejandro and Eric sitting in front)

Figure 9: Young scientists at the European Researchers' Night exploring how everyday objects like lemons can generate electricity, as they create their own lemon batteries.

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Figure 10: Children and Grown-Ups learning the basics of electricity by building lemon batteries, discovering how simple chemical reactions can power small devices.

[Medina Ćustić](#), Virtual Vehicle – [HiPE](#) & [Anna Zamecnik](#), Armengaud Innovate GmbH – [EM-TECH](#)

EARPA AUTUMN EVENT

Attending the EARPA Autumn Meeting 2024 on 30. September and 01. October in Brussels was a fantastic opportunity to meet with leading experts in the automotive research and innovation sector. The event kicked off with internal (member) meetings of EARPA's Foresight Groups, where key research topics in the automotive industry are discussed.

The public keynote session featured updates from the European Commission on the Horizon Europe work programme and the MAGELLAN project, as

well as discussions on [EARPA's ad hoc paper](#) and the circular economy in road transport. The final session featured success stories from European projects (NEMI, ASSESS and IPSY), demonstrating not only product innovation but also the positive impact on careers in the sector. A plenary session on Software-Defined Vehicles featuring the [FEDERATE](#) project looked ahead at how this technology will shape future research in Europe. The sessions highlighted the importance of research funding programmes such as Horizon Europe and showed how EU policies are driving sustainability and innovation.

Figure 11: EARPA autumn event © EARPA

With a focus on collaboration and future-focused research, EARPA's Autumn Meeting proved again to be a valuable experience for all attendees, and we look forward to the Spring Meeting in 2025!

[Medina Ćustić](#), Virtual Vehicle – [HiPE](#)

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SEE MOBILITY E-VOLV(E)ING

Smart Components for the Software-Defined Vehicle of the Future

As the automotive industry shifts towards increased digitalization, smart components are playing a key role in shaping the next generation of vehicles. The Software Defined Vehicle represents a transformative approach, where software innovation is key to increase vehicle performance, enable autonomous driving, and offer new services to users. In this webinar, you will hear from selected projects, all members to the E-VOLVE Cluster, that are paving the way for this technological shift. Each project will showcase how their innovative components contribute to the SDV concept of the Future, presenting their latest results, innovations, and future outlooks.

SEE MOBILITY E-VOLV(E)ING: Smart Components for the Software-Defined Vehicle of the Future

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the funding authority can be held responsible for them.

The projects presenting in this webinar are selected projects from the 2Zero partnership and members of the E-VOLVE cluster.

Ingrid Armengaud, Armengaud Innovate GmbH – [EM-TECH](#) / [HighScape](#)

E-VOLVE EV FOR LIFE, VALUE, EFFICIENCY

COMING UP

General Assembly

November 2024

Towards the sustainable vehicle era
Turin, [Registration](#)

November 8th, 2024

19th [A3PS](#) Conference, Eco-Mobility 2024
Sustainable Energy Carriers and Innovative Propulsion
Systems in a Circular Economy

November 14th – 15th, 2024

E-VOLVE Cluster webinar
“SEE MOBILITY E-VOLV(E)ING: Smart components for the
software-defined vehicle of the future”

November 22nd 2024

Next edition of the E-VOLVE Newsletter

January 2025

General Assembly

January 2025

General Assembly

January 2025

EM-TECH

General Assembly

January/February 2025

February 11th – 13th, 2025

EARPA Spring Meeting 2025
Brussels

March 4th – 5th, 2025

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